

THE ROLE OF VOCABULARY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract:In this article we have looked at the difference between teaching language structure and teaching vocabulary. We have discussed how counts of frequency alone are not enough to determine what words should be taught. We have seen that knowing a word means more than just knowing its meaning. Even that is problematical since meaning includes sense relations and context, for example. To know a word we also need to know about its use, how it is formed and what grammatical behavior it provokes. Above all, in this article, we have approached the idea of how vocabulary teaching and learning need to be emphasized in order for students to be competent language users.

Keywords:vocabulary, teaching vocabulary, learning vocabulary, word selection, role-play

The role of vocabulary for possessing a foreign language is very important. In any case, vocabulary gives the direct meaning of the object. Learning vocabulary in any language is often one of the most challenging areas, because it never ends! This is true even of our own native languages. We are constantly learning new words, as we could do in our mother tongue too if we continued to explore the language with the same strength after finishing school.

Practically in every foreign language lesson we work on expanding vocabulary, overreach specific word on a given topic. When working with the word, a certain system of actions is needed not only from the teacher, but also from the students. They are visual view of the word (visualization), sound perception (repetition of the teacher or speaker), written perception (writing the word to the dictionary, preferably in phrases and sentences). [1, 415]

In my class, I try to ensure that every student should understand that memorizing words would not be mechanical, that every word should be understood, correctly pronounced, read and written. This is facilitated by the correct and rational selection of techniques for working with vocabulary. Teaching vocabulary is the basis of language teaching. Lexicon is a collection of learned, formulated phrases and vocabulary. [2,160]

It is impossible to track or study the types of speech activity without having perfect vocabulary used as talking material.

The material is very important for speech. If there is no material, the conversation will not take place. You can listen to English language and understand its content based on what you are learning.[3,262] If a student does not know the words, he cannot get information, and the content of the conversation remains unclear.

1. There is a whole set of techniques for introducing lexical items:

- The introduction of nouns by demonstrating the designated objects or their images in the picture.

- Introduction of the verb with the help of illustrative movements or actions, facial expressions, pantomimes, etc.
 - Introduction of adjectives by displaying various objects or their images of pronounced quality (color, size, shape, picture, pattern).
 - Introduction of numerals using pictures with different numbers of objects, as well as hours, calendar, table, schedule.
 - Introduction of pronouns with the participation of trainees (personal and possessive pronouns), using the position of various objects in the room, the corresponding pictures.
 - Introduction of prepositions using the correlation of objects in the class, special illustrations, on which the objects are arranged differently.
 - Introducing interjections using playable situations or cartoon comics.
 - The introduction of collective words using words with specific meanings (cucumbers, tomatoes, vegetables)
 - Introduction of linguistic-cultural words with the help of description, interpretation of realities, the use of relevant visual materials. (photographs, pictures) Introduction of new words based on already known (complex words) by performing the necessary language operations, analysis and explanation.
2. It is necessary to use repeating exercises for more effective memorization of vocabulary.
- Read the words by inserting the missing letters.
 - Find the words in a crossword puzzle.
 - Find the words in chain word.
 - Insert the missing letters in the words.
 - Check the knowledge of words and phrases from each other.
 - Read the list of words, placing the words in alphabetical order.
 - Group new words in parts of speech.
3. Contribution of forming communicative competence of students' preparation in training exercises based on working with texts:
- Find in the text the words related to this topic.
 - Replace one of the sentence members with the words given.
 - Write down the words from the text according to certain characteristics (with prefixes, suffixes, compound words)
 - Find in the text words with a common root.
 - Find in the text a combination with the specified word.
 - Find new words in the text.
 - Guess the meaning of words similar to the Russian, and check the accuracy of the guesses in the dictionary.
 - Group words by analogy (for example, uniform verb control, the formation of compound words and phrases).
 - Write the words from the text with a common root.
 - Spread a compound word into components.
 - Make a letter analysis of the word.
4. At the stage of training and fixing vocabulary substitution and constructive exercises are very important.
- Fill in the blanks in the titles with words from the list.
 - Change the appropriate words or phrases instead of pictures in sentences.

- Replace the Russian words in the sentence with English.
- From the list of copies pick up the missing lines to the characters.
- Correct in the underlined words.
- Make a dialogue using a set of replicas.
- Make as many sentences as possible from the word set.

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